

Limos Orthography: A Teaching Guide for MTB-MLE in Early Grade Education in the Cordillera, Philippines

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ABSTRACT: The Philippines' Department of Education emphasized the importance of adopting Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in the K-12 program underlining mother tongue as the foundation of learning a second language. Through developmental research methods, a Limos Orthography developed as teaching guide in MTB-MLE in early grade level focused on Limos grammar, including alphabets, word charts (vowels and consonants), and spelling. Results of the study found that Limos language had distinct phonemes and structural elements despite having universal characteristics common with other languages. Findings suggest orthography as a teaching guide has potential to improve literacy rates and educational outcomes among Limos-speaking communities.

KEYWORDS: Language, workshop, education, alphabet, and grammar

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1. Introduction

The Philippines with the context of multilingual education, through the Department of Education deemed important to adopt and implement Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in K-12 Program. This action is supported by studies which indicate that utilizing one's mother tongue or native language offers a strong basis in promoting learning a second language. Research demonstrates that it is an effective instrument for improving learners' fluency, accuracy, and proficiency in listening, speaking, reading, and writing for meaning and confidence. Mother Tongue-Based-Multilingual Education is also the most vital reform for the country's basic education and school system as a whole that considered the salient feature of the K to 12 curriculum. In this regard, the use of Mother Tongue-Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) from Pre-school to Grade 3 will be taught in their mother tongue, or the first language they learned from birth. Implementation of Mother Tongue Based and Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE), in turn, forced recognition of the need to devise teaching methods, prepare learning guides, reading materials and most importantly to orient and train teachers in the said

program implementation. As a result, this revised curriculum changed any action or transitions that caused discomfort, obstacles, and difficulties for a lot of MTB-MLE teachers complaining of a rough movement far from the expectation of education officials. Relative to this, lack of trained teachers, scarcity or dearth of MTB teaching and learning materials, lack of proficiency in the language of instruction, and limited number of teachers who know the language of the learners are the reasons why despite a standard well-defined curriculum, MTB-MLE programs are not effectively sustained. Additionally, there have been studies that emphasize the lack of school supplies, such as books, chairs, and rooms, and the economic conditions. Another reason is the declining level of literacy in the country or literacy left at the crossroads status. Therefore, there is a need to raise goals for teaching reading and writing in terms of medium of instruction, especially in basic education at the elementary level. Moreover, studies and research show that primary level pupils, especially preschoolers, learn more easily if the language of instruction is their native language. If you stop to consider it, learning could be simpler because concepts and knowledge can be imparted more easily through the language that each person was born into rather than forcing them to speak English and Filipino. Subsequently, learners would be more receptive to learning if their original language is used as a teaching instrument, not just in the intellectual sense. Thus, by implementing MTB-MLE, it could guarantee all future generations raised and led fulfilling lives effectively. Based on previous research and experimentation, children learn and understand their lesson better when the language in the explanation is their "mother tongue" or first language, however, this is crucial for fostering and understanding in the classroom, preventing barriers to learning, and greatly assisting pupils if the language of instruction is their native tongue in order for them to receive high marks for comprehension and a true understanding of the tasks they are expected to complete. Furthermore, "mother tongue" would be the medium of instruction from pre-school to the third grade, in this case pupils do not have to adjust to a language that they do not fully know and, unfortunately, do not understand. Thus, considerably the most important reforms in the educational system are the MTB-MLE program. In relation to this matter, the most important part of any "Mother Tongue Language Education" initiative is the development of a writing system that is acceptable to the majority of native language speakers and the government that will encourage members of the mother tongue community to continue reading and writing in their language.

It was noted further in some research conducted regarding the effectiveness of using MTB-MLE (UNESCO (2003) that learners are more successful in learning to read and write using their first language than learners who did not learn it completely. This result corroborated with Walter and Dekker (2008) findings by showing that test results are greater for young learners using their first language than for those using English. The positive relationship between first language learning and second language learning confirmed also by Lartec, et al. (2013) allowing enough time to learn a first language results in more successful second

language acquisition. A major challenge here was the orthography system of each participating language. There was a need to further refine the grammatical rules used in instruction as their use in academic expands, along with the creation of first language materials that are culturally relevant and reflect local realities, intensive training of teachers in the use and speaking of the first language, and full participation and support of local government, parents, and the community. Language therefore is one of the most important factors affecting education. Thus, education for all cannot be achieved until students are given the opportunity to learn in their first language. The MTB-MLE program also provides a positive pathway for learners' success and equal opportunities in second language learning. Without a solid foundation in literacy across subjects, Love, K. (2008), a student will not be successful in his or her acquisition of knowledge when there is no available developed orthography which is an important requirement for the implementation of MTB-MLE.

Orthography is a complex system that sustains certain parts of history and facilitates understanding. Orthography refers to the relationship between a language and its script, encompassing the normative aspects of writing systems, including graphotactic and grapheme-phoneme correspondence rules. Alphabetic writing systems can be phonologically shallow or deep, and their orthographies can be categorized as regular or irregular (Scheerer, 1986, p. 262) as cited by Aloufi, A. (2019). Orthography, thus a systematic representation of language, including the placement of symbols, punctuation, capitalization, hyphenation, and other elements that can be regulated by a written basis or standard (Cahill & Karan, 2008). It is also a set of rules and practices, such as punctuation and capitalization rules (Coulmas, 1996) and that refers to the visual representation of language as having the basic phonological, syntactic, morphological, and semantic characteristics of a language (Seifart, 2006). Meanwhile, there is still little knowledge of how orthography affects speech production in seasoned L2 speakers, despite a recent notable increase in research on orthographic effects in second language (L2) phonology (Bassetti, Hayes-Harb & Escudero, 2015). The majority of research has been on beginning students or those learning new languages (Davidson, 2010; Hayes-Harb, Nicol, & Barker, 2010; Pytlyk, 2011). Studies with proficient L2 speakers usually focus on their ability to produce new words or pseudowords (Escudero & Wanrooij, 2010). Therefore, language and literacy requirements for children vary depending on the orthographies they use. A report by Llauro, A. et al. (2020) on comparing reading decoding and single-word spelling across orthographies has significantly advanced our understanding of these processes, building on examples from Moll et al. (2014) and Landerl et al. (2019). However, there is still limited knowledge on how orthographic variations and language typologies interact to affect writing performance and writing development. Relative to this, Harsanti (2020), stated that orthography plays a crucial role in teaching language literacy to young learners, particularly in developing their spelling abilities through provision of the right stimuli that helps children learn to respond with correct spellings. Additionally,

understanding orthography enhances children's sensitivity to the spelling of new words, even those they haven't encountered before, Liao, C. H. (2006).

The impact of orthography on the acquisition of literacy skills cannot be overestimated which affects reading (Perfetti & Liu, 2005) and also plays a very important role in phonological awareness skills (Zaretsky & Barshalom, 2010). The influence of orthography on the phonological representation of words in the lexicon has been documented (Taft & Hambly, 1985). In all experiments, the learning of the sound is facilitated or accelerated if the correct spelling is seen, and the interpretation becomes effective even without the correct spelling because the readers are given an orthographic image that is important in the formation of the sound in the mind (Aaron, 2004). Orthography further improves literacy, and the number of publications on the subject shows that, in the past, attention to orthography has expanded quickly due to growing awareness of endangered languages (Cahill & Karan, 2008). The growth or evolution of orthography is one of the most significant subjects since it is a vital part of literacy (Page, 2013). Considerations for the cultivation of orthography have been put forth by a number of researchers; these are mentioned by Wakat (2014) and Guerin (2008) in orthographic design and by Hooley (1974), McGregor (1986), Rehg (2004), Seifart (2006), Simons (1994), and Stubbs (1980) in relation to the use of technology, social and cultural performance, psycholinguistic reception, and orthography.

In the studies conducted by some researchers, they brought out some methods to cultivate orthography. The cultivation of orthography is a free model of an orthography written in an unbiased manner and a scientific process that considers "alphabetic phonemic writing" as ideal orthography (Sebba, 2007); therefore, the cultivation of orthography requires the involvement of community citizens (Page, 2013). The cultivation of orthography in a participatory model works for an orthography that involves the socio-cultural process related to the use of language in the context of citizens in the community (Page, 2013). Bos, Bos, and Page (2008). It also includes meetings in the village related to language awareness, a workshop on orthography cultivation, the formation of language committees for identifying some difficult parts of orthography, and a spelling check. When analyzing and addressing some other orthographic problems, Page (2013) used similar measures.

In the research of Markowski (2009), a linguistic consultant was introduced to the So group. The various principles of good orthography and explanations of the sounds of the So language are presented and compared with the Thai language. The committee's selection criteria are as follows: members are So citizens, fluent in this language, able to read and write Thai, and have a role or position in the So community. Community involvement further increases trust, stabilizes, and intensifies the feeling that they were accepted and belong to the community, Page (2013); Markowski (2009). The participants feel proud of their language (Bos, Bos,

and Page 2008), and guided activities, lots of examples, and repetition play a huge role in the cultivation of orthography.

Page (2013) found in his study that some of the challenging events are the refusal of the elders in the community to participate in the workshop, even if they have been told, because of their fear and because they are not familiar with the script that is being used. Eira (1998) also agreed with this statement due to the unfamiliarity of the script used. The community believes that it is difficult to write, especially for those who have not experienced formal education, thus preventing them from joining or participating in the workshop. Additionally, Markowski (2009) stated that some of the challenges in cultivating So language orthography are cultural differences in learning and writing style.

In the phases and challenges facing the cultivation of orthography, the participation of community members is indispensable to a full understanding of the language and its orthography. Likewise, cultivation of orthography necessarily requires that the participants are members of the community and the informants must be fluent in the first language, or "mother tongue," even if they cannot read and write, as long as they are fluent in the first language and knowledgeable and proficient in other languages. Language experts, government representatives, and citizens from neighboring languages are very important sources of information, especially if they have undergone the process of cultivating their writing system (Malone, 2004). Meanwhile, orthography is part of society; it contains tradition and community culture (Casquite (2013) noted that a systematic approach to the cultivation of orthography is a very important component for starting the MTB-MLE program. In this regard, Ferguson (1986) cited by Page (2013), stating that the very first step in developing a language is the development of a writing system that is also related to orthography. However, many of the languages of the country do not yet have orthography. The Department of Education issued a letter stating that nineteen (19) out of the 179 languages of the country were used as the medium of instruction and taught as a subject; therefore, the need to cultivate the orthography of different languages in the country is appropriate, including the Limos language.

Limos is one of the Kalinga languages spoken by people living in the Limos community in the Cordillera Region in northern Luzon, Philippines. It is known as Linimos by its users and Linimos Kalinga. It is a language spoken by approximately thirty thousand (30,000) people who live in barangays near the Saltan River in the town of Pinukpuk. Many efforts have been made to preserve and develop this language; books and materials written in Limos have been published. The "Pagbilogon ta Datum Long-ang" (SIL, 1997), Kalinga (Linimos): Introduction and Wordlist (Weins, 1995), "Manta Ikun Taku si Labit" (SIL, 1976), "Basaon Taku nat Pilipino" (SIL, 1997), "San Mampatubut Ung" (SIL, 1976), "Mun-aaligon Taku Datum Agud un Nasukatan si Osan Kanglit" (SIL, 1997), Phonology of Filipino and Limos: A Review and Comparison (Ngislawan, 2007), "Allalim un Mambalikas

(Folktales that speak): A story in Limos-Kalinga (Awingan, Balutoc at Banatao, 1977).

Based on the materials and the works produced, the standardization of spelling needs to be explained. Despite the proliferation of literature, the Limos language does not yet have an official orthography. If there is, it is unofficial, and nothing has been published. With respect to the Department of Education in 2009, which presented documents showing the successful implementation of the MTB-MLE program and its clear demand for a life of orthography widely accepted by students in the community, In this discourse, a research questions be raised; Q1- How does basic orthography of Limos influence the efficacy of teaching the indigenous language in ethnic rural educational settings?; Q2- What are the observations of educators and pupils about the ease of learning by means of Limos with the new orthographic style associated with outdated approaches?; Q3- In what actions does the implementation of young learners Limos orthography impact in preservation and progress of the native language within the community?

Hence, this study aims to develop a Limos orthography to enhance educational outcomes and literacy in Limos-speaking communities, guiding the teaching of MTB-MLE. Specifically, it seeks to: (a) raise awareness and encourage community participation in the preservation and development of the Limos orthography; (b) gather MTB-MLE teaching materials for use in Limos-speaking barangays in Pinukpuk, Kalinga; and (c) assist linguistic researchers and educators in creating teaching tools for the first language in elementary schools.

2. Methodology

This part presents the research methodologies and procedure to attain results that will answer the research problem in this study.

Respondent and Localization

One hundred (100) respondents participated in this study; seventy-five (75) were from the barangays of Pinukpuk, Kalinga Province, that speak Limos language, which includes the barangays of Asibanglan, Ballayangon, Baay, and Limos. In addition, respondents included three (3) from the Summer Institute of Linguistics (SIL), twelve (12) from the Department of Education and six (6) other languages close to the Limos language, and four (4) non-Limos language teachers. All expected respondents participated in the said workshop.

Most participants were Limos speakers and elders from barangays where Limos is spoken. Elders are considered key sources of reliable data for language studies (Malone, 2004). The study also included proficient Limos speakers, non-Limos speakers, local government representatives, members of the Philippine Commission on Languages, language specialists, and a native Limos speaker from

the Summer Institute of Linguistics. Additionally, community members involved in education were included, as the study aimed to develop an orthography that supports the MTB-MLE program, enhancing literacy and student comprehension in their native language

Data Collection

Data gathering focused on developing orthography using methods from Wakat (2014) and the community-based approach of Page (2013) and Bos et al. (2008). The National Orthography (2014) served as the primary reference for selecting topics and their sequence, with adjustments made to meet the respondents' needs (Page, 2013).

Before the workshop, a phonological analysis of the Kuy language was conducted based on studies by Page (2013) and Bos et al. (2008). A survey questionnaire was distributed to 25 Limos-speaking professionals (15 teachers, 4 Agriculture graduates, 5 Forestry graduates, and 1 Business Administration graduate) to gather words used in the workshop, along with interviews from elderly Limos speakers. The survey consisted of three parts: listing Limos words with translations and parts of speech, identifying action words and their suffixes, and providing Limos sentences with Filipino translations. The collected data, including folktales such as Sudatun Duwan Abeng, were analyzed using the National Orthography (2014) and compared to the Mother Tongue Teaching Guide. The analysis, based on 268 words, identified key issues for the workshop

On the first day of the workshop, the researcher explained the importance and purpose of the workshop. Explaining the Orthography of Philippines National Language supervised by an NCCA staff member who is often invited to seminars to be a lecturer on the national language. The lecture includes the phonology of the national language and how the translation of words is done in the Filipino language to serve as a guide and show the difference between the national language and the Limos language. The participants were grouped based on their barangay of origin. Formed four groups to represent the four barangays in Pinukpuk that speak Limos: Asibanglan, Baay, Ballayangon, and Limos. In each group, the researcher presented a copy of the word list, and they were asked to translate each word written or recorded. After they finished translating the words, the researchers requested the participants to listen to a folktale read by a representative from the Limos-speaking SIL. Each group was given a piece of writing paper and would translate the word that the reader of the folktale would emphasize. The three folktales read by one of the representatives of SI were the ones that the participants chose. The folk tales came from the participants because one of them had a hidden copy of a folk tale in Limos, and this was the story they agreed to bring to the workshop and used the words for this study.

In the workshop, the participation of representatives from the National Commission for Culture and the Arts (NCCA), the Summer Institute of Linguistics (SIL), and Philippine Commission on Languages was vital because the representatives helped in the technical aspect of the research. The representative from NCCA was the lecturer about the national orthography, while the representatives from SIL and KWF were the references for the respondents in their discussion.

On the second day workshop, each group continued their unfinished tasks and received guiding questions for developing orthography using the Orthography of the National Language (2014) as a reference, they answered the questions, ensuring coherence and appropriateness. A discussion followed, with each group's representative writing their answers. If discrepancies arose, the group with the different response was asked to explain until consensus was reached. The researcher presented the findings, supported by interview data and interpretive observations, aiming to provide a comprehensive description of participants' experiences and perceptions (Hale & Astolfi, 2007). Figure 1 illustrates the study procedure;

Figure 1. Framework of the Procedure

3. Results

As a result of using the collected data among the participants, the Limos orthography is so advanced that they use it as the MTB-MLE teaching guide. Orthography focuses on the Limos grapheme, consisting of letters and non-letters, syllables and syllabification, spelling, hyphenation, consonants, vowels, stress, words that are spelled the same but pronounced differently.

Grapheme

Philippines Commission on Languages (2014) noted that the use of orthography is the application of graphemes to represent oral and written statements. In addition, Meletis (2019) stated that graphemes are units of writing

which are lexically distinctive, have linguistic value (mostly by referring to phonemes, syllables, morphemes, etc.), and are minimal. In this regard, a grapheme is a set or group of parts in a writing system consisting of letters and symbols.

Letters: Vowels and Consonants.

A letter is a symbol of a speech sound. It consists of vowels and consonants. A series of letters is called an alphabet. According to the respondents, the Limos alphabet consists of 28 letters, which can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Limos Alphabet

Aa	Bb	Cc	Dd	Ee
"ey"	"bl"	"si"	"di"	"e"
Ff	Gg	Hh	li	Jj
"ef"	"dyl"	"eyts"	"ay"	"dyey"
Kk	Ll	Mm	Nn	Ññ
"key"	"el"	"em"	"en"	"enye"
NGng	Oo	Pp	Qq	Rr
"endyl"	"o"	"pi"	"kyu"	"ar"
Ss	Tt	Uu	Vv	Ww
"es"	"ti"	"yu"	"vi"	"dobolyu"
Xx	Yy	Zz		
"eks"	"way"	"zi"		

The terminology of the letters is based on Philippine Orthography (2014) where Limos alphabet consists of twenty-three (23) consonants. They were as follows: Bb, Cc, Dd, Ff, Gg, Hh, Jj, Kk, Ll, Mm, Nn, Ññ, NGng, Pp, Qq, Rr, Ss, Tt, Vv, Ww, Xx, Yy, and Zz. According to the respondents, the letters Ff, Jj, Vv, and Xx are from the Indies language, and the letters Zz, Cc, Qq, and Nñ are from the Spanish language. It comprises five vowels: Aa, Ee, li, Oo, and Uu. The tongue, lips, and jaw are used in pronouncing vowels. When pronouncing it, the position of the tongue changes.

Table 2. Chart of Limos Consonants

Point of Articulation	Point of Articulation		
	labia	Palata	Glotal
	l	l	key
Closed and voiceless	p	t	?
Semi-vowel	b	d	
Accented sounds	:b	d	
voiceless	s		
Lateral voiceless	l		

Semi –vowel voiceless

w

y

Limos Consonants:

For the researcher to further explain the Limos grapheme, there are times when this study will inevitably include a little knowledge about phonology. Consonants of Limos language- based on the table, were sounds represented by the letters p, t, and k, and the accented sound (?) is closed and voiceless in the way of articulation. At the point of articulation, /p/ is labial, /t/ is palatal, /k/ is vocal (velar), and () is the glottal or accented sound. . The sounds /b/, /d/, and /g/ g/are stopped and voiced in the manner of articulation at the point of diction /b/ b/is labial, /d/ is palatal, and /g/ g/is velar. The consonants m, n, and ng are nasal at the point of articulation. The /m/ is labial, /n/ is palatal, and /p/ is noun-velar. The /s/ is primitive voiceless and palatal by point of articulation; the /l/ is silent and palatal. The vowels /w/ and /y/ are voiceless; /w/ is labial and palatal, and /y/ is palatal by point of articulation.

Table 3. *Limos Vowel Chart*

	Front	Central	Back
High	I		u
Middle	E		o
Low		a	

The preceding table displayed the vowel chart for Limos. The tongue is positioned high-front when pronouncing the vowel /i/. The front and center vowel is /e/. The tongue is positioned low-central and the lips have a slightly circular shape when speaking the vowel /a/. The tongue is in the middle and at the back of the mouth when pronouncing the vowel /o/. The lips are round.

Replacement of E and I

Replacement of E and I showed that bateled (hill), kandelu (pot), and emes (smile) can also be spelled as batelid, kandilu, at imes. One of the participants suggested that I could be replaced with E which was agreed upon by the other participants. It follows the rules when a syllable occurs in two phonemes without stress, Santiago and Tiangco (1997). The i and e are two similar sounds because the front of the tongue does the work in pronouncing them. The use of /i/ to represent /e/ cannot be changed because i and e are allophones.

Table 4. *Words with E and I*

Data gathered	Agreed		
ae	and	i	
Bateled batelid (hill)		Batelid (hill)	Bateled (Hill)
Emes(smile)		imes(smile)	imes/emes (smile)
Kandelu (pot)		kandilu(pot)	kandilu/kandilu

The table showed that the exchange of E and I does not only occur in Filipino language but also in native languages of the Philippines, such as the Limos language. Therefore, it indicates that the development of Limos orthography was useful and helpful in teaching MTB-MLE. These findings conformed to reports of the Philippine Commission on Languages (2014), which stated that. The change of E to I and O to U is a natural occurrence in the indigenous languages of the Philippines. Philippine Commission on Languages (2014) also thought that it is part of the discipline of language and the rule to exclude E from I and O from U.

According to Wien's (1976), the pronunciation of the vowel /e/ is like the first sound of the English word "end." Normally, the vowel /a/ is pronounced like the English word "are," but if it is found in a closed syllable preceded by /c/ it is pronounced like the /a/ of the English word "cat." If the syllable /o/ is found in a similar background, it is pronounced like the German word "Schon." The vowel /o/ does not appear at the end of a word, but in such a position, the vowel /u/ is pronounced between the pronunciation of /o/ in the English word "old" and /u/ in the word "blue." According to Philippine Commission on Languages (2014), such discipline would stop the slang behavior of I and E at the beginning of words such as istilo (style) instead of "estilo", and minudo instead of "menudo." Thus, it would prevent the habit of replacing U with O, like the word "kuryente" instead of "koryente", "murado" instead of "morado," "sombbrero" instead of "sumbrero," and "pulitika" instead of "politika" (p. 31).

Replacement of O and U

There were differences in the spelling of the words puwug (knee), balituk (gold), lubu (nest), simpulu (ten) and tulu (three). However, the O and U in Limos Kalinga are freely interchangeable, and their meaning does not change. Limos can use it both in their speeches.

Table 5. *Words with O and U*

Data Gathered		Agreed
O	U	
Powog	puwug (knee)	puwug/puwog
	balituk (gold)	balituk/balitok
Lobu	lubu (nest)	lubu/lubo
Opat		opat
Tolu	tulu (three)	tulu
Simpolu	simpulu (ten)	simpulo

Spelling

Based on the collected data, the spelling of words in Limos is based on how they call the letter. Each name is based on the order of the letters in the word. Syllables, abbreviations, acronyms, initials, scientific and mathematical symbols, and other terminology could be found in Table 6.

Table 6. Spelling in Limos

A. Words	Takikiling (November)	/capital ti-ey-key-ay-keyay-el-ay-endyi/
	Kagwa (Tuesday)	/capital key-ey-dyi- dobolyu-ey/
	Puwug (eyebrow)	/pi-yu-dobolyu-yu-dyi/
	Oyok (armpit)	/o-way-o-key/
B. Syllable	Tu	/ti-yu/
	Lo	/el-o/
	Nom	/en-o-em/
	Pat	/pi-ey-ti/
	Pu	/pi-yu/
C. Acronym	KAELCO (Kalinga-Apayao Electric Cooperative)	/capital key-capital ey-capital-i-capital el-capital si-capital o/

	TAFAMULCO (Tabuk Farmers Multi-Purpose Cooperative)	/capital ti- capital ey-capital em -capital pi capital si- capital o/
	DOH (Department of Health)	/capital di- capital o -capital eyts/
	DILG (Department of Interior and Local Government)	/capital di- capital ay- capital el- capital dyi/
D. Abbreviation	Bb. (Binibini)	/capital bi-bi-tuldok/
	G. (Ginoo)	/capital dyi-tuldok/
	Gng. (Ginang)	/capital dyi-endyi-tuldok/
	Sen. (Senator)	/capital es-i-en-tuldok/
E. Initial	FVR (Fidel Valdez Ramos)	/capital ef-capital vi-capital ar/ capital dyey-capital ey capital es/
E1.Things and people)	JCB (Jocel Callangan Baac)	/capital dyey-capital si- capital bi/
	TV (Television)	/capital ti-capital vi/
	CP (Cellular Phone)	/capital si-capital pi/
	KSU (Kalinga State University)	/capital key-capital es- capital yu/
	NCIP (National Commission Indigenous People)	/capital en-capital-si capital i capital pi/
	KBC (Kalinga Bodong Council)	/capital key- capital bi- capital si/
	STS (Saint Teresita's School)	/capital es-capital ti-capital- es/
	KA (Kalinga Academy)	/capital key- capital ey/
F. Science and Mathematics symbol	Cu (Copper)	/capital si-yu/
	Ag (Silver)	capital ey-dyi/
	Fe (Iron)	/capital ef-i/
	Lb (Pound)	/capital el-bi/
	M (Meter)	/capital em/
	Ha (hectare)	capital eyts-ey/

4. Discussion

The movement of the tongue extends, can be shortened and bowed, retracted, forwarded, and raised according to the vowel formation (Santiago and Tiangco, 1991). The admission of the Limos language in the letters C, F, I, Ñ, Q, V, Z, H, and R that come from the English, Spanish, and Filipino languages help its

development because the language is dynamic, and associated with this is the borrowing of letters that are not included in phonology. The letters H and R are not in Limos, acquired from the Filipino language, and these letters are native to our national language. Borrowing the Limos language from the mentioned letters is highly helpful and can be used in proper nouns, which the workshop participants confirmed throughout the discussion and shared ideas. The letter NG native to Limos is essential in their alphabet because many words in the Limos language utilize the sound NG. In the Filipino language, NG is important letter because it can be found in the initial, middle, and final part of the word (Santiago & Tiangco, 1991)

On the other hand, the manner of articulation describes how the speech organs used work and how the breath comes out of the mouth or the nose when pronouncing any of the consonant phonemes, while the point of articulation describes which part of the mouth experiences the momentary stopping or interruption of the outgoing air in pronouncing a consonant (Santiago, 1991). It is evident that in Limos, the way they pronounce the letter is under the English pronunciation, except for Nñ ("enye"), which is pronounced in Spanish. In relation to this result, as for the vowel /u/, the tongue is in an upward and backward position. This could describe the arrangement of the tongue in the pronunciation of vowels by their progression, contraction, and evaluation (Wien's, 1976a).

The exchange of E and I does not only occur in the Filipino language but also in the native languages of the Philippines, such as the Limos language. Therefore, it indicates that the development of Limos orthography was useful and helpful in teaching MTB-MLE. Relative to this, the Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino (2014) stated that the change of E to I and O to U is a natural occurrence in the indigenous languages of the Philippine Language Commission (2014) also thought that it is part of the discipline of the tongue and the rule to exclude E from I and O from U.

According to Wien's (1976), the pronunciation of the vowel /e/ was like the first sound of the English word "end". Normally, the vowel /a/ is pronounced like the English word "are," but if it is found in a closed syllable preceded by /c/ it is pronounced like the /a/ of the English word "cat." If the syllable /o/ is found in a similar background, it is pronounced like the German word "Schon." The vowel /o/ does not appear at the end of a word, but in such a position, the vowel /u/ is pronounced between the pronunciation of /o/ in the English word "old" and /u/ in the word "blue." According to Philippine Language Commission (2014), such discipline will stop the slang behavior of I and E at the beginning of words such as *istilo* (style) instead of "estilo", and *minudo* instead of "menudo." It will also prevent the habit of replacing U with O, like *twordsord* "kuryente" instead of "koryente", "murado" instead of "morado," "sombbrero" instead of "sumbrero," and "pulitika" instead of "politika" (p. 31).

Furthermore, there were differences in the spelling of the words *puwug* (knee), *balituk* (gold), *lubu* (nest), *simpulu* (ten), and *tulu* (three). However, the O and

U in Limos Kalinga are freely interchangeable, and their meaning does not change. Limos can use it both in their speech. Moreover, the words Takikiling (November), Kagwa (Tuesday), puwug (knee), kimat (eyebrow), and oyok (armpit) are spelled as ti-ei-kei-ai-kei-ai-el-ai-en-dzi, kei-ei-dzi-'d^belju;-ei, pi- ju'd^belju;-dzi, kei-ai-em-ei-ti and o-wai-eu-kei, the same syllable in tu, lo, nom, pat, pu are spelled as ti-ju, el-o, en-o-em, pi:-ei-ti, pi-ju.

The acronyms KAELCO (Kalinga- Apayao Electric Cooperative), TAFAMULCO (Tabuk Multi-Purpose Cooperative). DOH (Department of Health), DILG (Department of Interior and Local Government) are spelled out as capital kei-capital ei- capital i: - capital el- capital si:- capital o, capital ti- capital ei- capital ef-capital ei- capital em- capital ju- capital el- capital si:- capital o, capital di:- capital o-capital eit}, and capital di:- capital ai- capital el- capital dzi:. The abbreviations like Bb. (Binibini), G. (Ginoo), Gng. (Ginang), Sen. (Senator), Atty. (Attorney) are spelled capital bi:-bi:, capital dzi:, capital dzi:-en-dzi:, capital es- i:-en, and capital ei-ti-ti-wai.: capital dzei- capital ei- capital. es, and capital dzei- capital si: - capital bi:, the same spelling rules will be used for initials such as TV (Television), CP (Cellular Phone), which were spelled as capital ti:- capital vi:, and capital si:- capital pi:.

The initials of the institutions such as KSU (Kalinga State University), NCIP (National Commission on Indigenous Peoples), KBC (Kalinga Bodong Council), STS (Saint Teresita's School), and KA (Kalinga Academy) are spelled capital key-capital es-capital yu, capital en capital si-capital ay-capital pi, es-capital ti-capital es, and capital key-capital ey.

Similar spelling rules were also used in scientific and mathematical symbols such as Cu (Copper), Ag (Silver), Fe (Iron), m (meter), and ha (hectare); these could be spelled as capital si-yu capital ey-dyi, capital ef-ay, el-bi, em and eyts-ey..

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate the advanced nature of the Limos orthography, making it a useful teaching guide for mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE). The Limos orthography encompasses graphemes that include both letters and non-letters, focusing on syllables, spelling, consonants, vowels, stress, and homographs. The Limos alphabet comprises 28 letters, including 23 consonants and 5 vowels, with influences from English, Spanish, and Filipino. The consonant sounds are articulated through various points in the mouth, and the vowel sounds are shaped by the tongue's position. The orthographic variations between letters such as E and I, and O and U, reflect natural linguistic occurrences within the Limos language, which align with the patterns observed in other Philippine languages. These findings indicate that the development of Limos orthography is beneficial for educational purposes, particularly in enhancing the teaching and learning processes within Limos-speaking communities especially for learners in the

first to third grades of elementary education who are under the MTB-MLE program. Moreover, the adoption of standardized spelling and pronunciation rules for acronyms, abbreviations, and scientific symbols further supports the systematic approach to Limos orthography, making it an effective tool for literacy and education.

Furthermore, to make sure that this orthography created through research is suitable for usage, it must go through more examination and improvement. It is advised to test the developed orthography and arrange a language conference. It was also suggested that the authorities' concern approved and confirmed so that it may serve as a reference for creating curriculum, instructional materials, and teaching strategies. Relatively, it would serve as a manual for instructing learners in Limos as a subject and a medium of instruction in primary grades school.

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